

Real-Time Decay Heat Estimation in Load-Following Transients Using the Adaptive SCRAM-Curve Method

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the *adaptive method*, which estimates transient decay heat from a precomputed SCRAM curve without reliance on decay heat standards or real-time nuclide tracking. The method is refined and extended in two ways: (i) application to transients with both decreasing and increasing power levels, and (ii) correction for long-duration transients where the accumulation of long-lived precursors alters the equilibrium decay heat.

Verification is performed using the Monte Carlo depletion solver Serpent, including simulated power drop and excursion events, as well as a load-following operation. The adaptive method reproduces reference solutions with high accuracy while providing a simplified framework suitable for real-time system code simulations and advanced reactor applications.

Keywords: decay heat, real-time simulation, transient analysis, load-following, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate estimation of decay heat is essential for ensuring the safety of nuclear reactors during transients and accident scenarios. For emergency shutdowns (SCRAM), precomputed decay heat curves (SCRAM curves) can be used directly in transient calculations. When SCRAM does not occur (e.g., unprotected transients or load-following) and the transient power is not known in advance, such curves cannot be precomputed. Alternatives include integrating depletion solvers with detailed nuclide tracking or employing simplified dynamic models supplementing a decay heat standard, but these approaches are often restricted by software or resource limitations.

To overcome these limitations, the preceding study [1] introduced the *adaptive method*, which estimates transient decay heat from a precomputed SCRAM curve without reliance on standards or real-time depletion. The present work refines this method and adds two extensions: (i) treatment of transients with varying power levels, and (ii) correction for long-duration transients where depletion modifies the equilibrium decay heat. Verification is carried out with the Monte Carlo depletion solver Serpent [2] for load-following scenarios and long on-power transients.

The adaptive method for shutdowns is outlined in Section 2, the extension to varying powers in Section 3, and the extension to long transients in Section 4. A one-week load-following demonstration is presented in Section 5, and the key findings are summarized in Section 6.

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2. ADAPTIVE METHOD FOR SHUTDOWN TRANSIENTS

2.0.1. SCRAM Curve Definition

The normalized decay heat curve is defined as the transient decay heat $H(t)$ relative to the initial total power $P(0)$:

$$h(t) = \frac{H(t)}{P(0)} = \frac{H(t)}{P^{\text{fiss}}(0) + H(0)}. \quad (1)$$

When fission power drops to zero at the transient onset, i.e. $P^{\text{fiss}}(t > 0) = 0$, then $h(t)$ is referred to as the SCRAM curve.

2.1. Assumption of Proportionality

When fission power does not immediately drop to zero but decreases gradually, additional decay heat precursors are produced, thereby extending the exponentially decaying curve over time. The method assumes that if the fission power drops by ΔP_i^{fiss} (i.e. $\Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}} < 0$) at time t_i , then only a

$$\frac{-\Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}}}{P^{\text{fiss}}(0)}$$

fraction of the decay heat precursors starts to decay, while the remaining precursors stay in equilibrium. In the case of an n -step shutdown (i.e. fission power reaches zero after n discrete steps),

$$P^{\text{fiss}}(0) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}}, \quad (2)$$

the precursors can be divided into n "timing" groups. Each group i remains in equilibrium until its corresponding time step t_i , after which its precursors start to decay. The decay of each group produces the same decay heat curve (SCRAM curve), but shifted in time according to its start. Consequently, the decay heat curve of group i takes the conditional form:

$$h_i(t) = \begin{cases} h(0), & t < t_i, \\ h(t - t_i), & t \geq t_i. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The decay heat curve of each group is weighted with its fission power drop and summed up to obtain the total transient decay heat:

$$H(t) = - \sum_{i=1}^n h_i(t) \cdot \Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}} = \sum_{i=1}^n H_i(t). \quad (4)$$

To construct the transient decay heat using this method, one must know t_i and ΔP_i^{fiss} in advance, while ensuring that all fission power is removed at some point during the transient, as expressed in Equation (2).

2.2. Complement Decay Heat

To circumvent these constraints, the concept of *complement heat* is introduced. It represents the additional decay heat that would have been generated if the power had remained constant. The complement heat curve for a precursor fraction that decays over time can be expressed as

$$H_i^{\text{C}}(t) = H_i(0) - H_i(t). \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. Visualization of the adaptive method. Complement heat $H_j^C(t)$ is introduced at each power reduction step, and the superposition of these contributions yields the total transient decay heat $H(t)$.

2.2.1. Adaptive Algorithm for Shutdowns

Based on the above definitions, the following procedure was implemented, which is also illustrated in Figure 1:

1. A decay heat timetable, $H(t_j)$, is created at the start of the simulation. It contains the temporal evolution of decay heat until the end of the simulation. Initially, the table is populated with constant decay heat values, corresponding to steady-state conditions where the power remains unchanged and decay heat precursors are in equilibrium:

$$H(t) := H(0). \quad (6)$$

This constant state remains until the first power change, depicted as the *red segment* ($t < t_1$) in Figure 1.

2. At each calculation step j , the change in fission power during the previous step is checked:
 - (a) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} < 0$, the decay heat table is updated using Equation (5) starting from t_j (see Figure 1 for $j = 1, 2$):

$$H(t) := H(t) - H_j^C(t). \quad (7)$$

- (b) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} = 0$, the decay heat table remains unchanged, since $H_j^C(t) = 0$.
- (c) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} > 0$, the method assumes the beginning of a new transient. All subsequent table values are set to a constant level of decay heat:

$$H(t \geq t_j) := h(0) \cdot P(t_j). \quad (8)$$

3. The instantaneous decay heat is extracted from the updated table. Repeat step 2.

With this adaptive method, the decay heat for non-SCRAM shutdown scenarios can be calculated in real time, even though only the SCRAM decay heat behavior is known in advance. In the previous study [1], the cumulative growth of precursors and their contribution to decay heat was still uncertain. Therefore, the method was not considered applicable to transients with rising power. This limitation is now addressed by introducing the *growth curve* in the following section.

2.3. Verification Results for Shutdowns

The present paper focuses on decay heat estimation in load-following scenarios and long on-power transients. Results for pure shutdown cases, where power decreases gradually, have been reported in previous studies [1, 3] and are not repeated here.

3. METHOD EXTENSION TO VARYING POWERS

3.1. Nuclide Growth Curve

When the fission power is increased step-wise ($\Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}} > 0$), a new group of precursors can be virtually added to the system. This group is initially “empty”, contributing no decay heat: $H_i(0) = 0$.

The initial growth of precursors is assumed to be dominated by short-lived nuclides that are effectively produced directly by fission (including the daughters of very short-lived parents). The evolution of such a nuclide with number density $N(t)$ follows the production–decay balance:

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = \gamma \Sigma_f \phi - \lambda N(t), \quad (9)$$

where γ is the fission yield, $\Sigma_f \phi$ is the fission rate (proportional to ΔP_i^{fiss}), and λ is the decay constant. Solving Equation (9) with the initial “empty” condition $N(0) = 0$ gives the growth curve:

$$N(t) = \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f \phi}{\lambda} (1 - e^{-\lambda t}), \quad (10)$$

which approaches steady state exponentially:

$$N(t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f \phi}{\lambda}. \quad (11)$$

Since the decay heat contribution of this nuclide is proportional to its growth rate $N(t)$, the additional contribution to decay heat can be described by this growth curve.

3.2. Nuclide Decay Curve

To illustrate the relation between the growth and decay curves, consider the pure radioactive decay of a nuclide without further production:

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = -\lambda N(t). \quad (12)$$

Starting from the steady-state precursor inventory, $N(0) = \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f \phi}{\lambda}$, obtained from the production–decay balance, the solution is

$$N(t) = \frac{\gamma \Sigma_f \phi}{\lambda} e^{-\lambda t}. \quad (13)$$

3.3. Curvature symmetry

In Equation (10), if the expression is multiplied by -1 and the equilibrium value $\frac{\gamma \Sigma_f \phi}{\lambda}$ is added, the growth curve becomes equivalent to the decay curve of Equation (13). In other words, both curves represent the same exponential function, but shifted and mirrored vertically. Consequently, the transient decay heat contributions from precursor growth and decay share the same exponential form.

For a realistic fuel composition, the overall decay heat curve is also of exponential nature, since it is the sum of exponential contributions from all precursors. Accordingly, the growth and decay curves of the total decay heat exhibit identical curvature. This is demonstrated in Figure 2 using a Serpent calculation of the FFTF, a sodium-cooled fast reactor with mixed-oxide fuel.

Figure 2. Comparison of decay heat curves. Left: short-term ($t < 10^4$ s). Right: long-term ($t > 10^4$ s).

In the first 10^4 s (Figure 2, left), when short-lived precursors are the dominant contributors to decay heat dynamics, the cumulative decay curve (SCRAM curve) and the inverted cumulative growth curve are in near-perfect alignment. The discrepancy observed at longer times ($t > 10^4$ s, Figure 2, right) is discussed in Section 4.

3.4. Adaptive Algorithm Extension to Varying Powers

This symmetry enables the use of a single SCRAM curve to estimate decay heat in transients with both decreasing and increasing power levels. With this, the second step of the adaptive algorithm (Section 2.2.1) can be simplified to:

1. At the start of the simulation, initialize the decay heat table: $H(t) := H(0)$.
2. At each calculation step j , check the change in fission power:
 - (a) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} \neq 0$, update the decay heat table: $H(t) := H(t) - H_j^C(t)$.
 - (b) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} = 0$, leave the decay heat table unchanged.
3. Extract the instantaneous decay heat from the updated table and repeat step 2.

3.5. Verification Results for Varying Powers

A 3D single-assembly model of an FFTF driver fuel assembly (reported in [4]) was created using Serpent. This model was employed to perform depletion calculations, yielding:

1. A SCRAM curve required as input for the adaptive method.
2. A decay heat curve of the test scenario, used as the reference solution in the verification process.

The decay heat was also computed using the adaptive method, which utilized the SCRAM curve from Serpent together with the postulated fission power curve. The SCRAM curve, represented as a sum of exponential functions, was provided as input, while the transient power was processed in real time by the method.

A test case was devised with fission power changing rapidly (step-wise) both up and down, followed by a full shutdown at $t = 4000$ s (see Figure 3, top). The reference solution from Serpent and the corresponding result of the adaptive method are shown in the middle of Figure 3. The adaptive method reproduced the

decay heat with high accuracy, as the difference $\delta(t)$ did not exceed 0.3%. The $\delta(t)$ was defined as the difference in decay heat relative to the initial reference value:

$$\delta(t) = \frac{H(t) - H^{\text{ref.}}(t)}{H^{\text{ref.}}(0)} \quad (14)$$

Figure 3. Decay heat in stepwise power up-and-down transient with final shutdown at 4000 s. Top: fission power. Middle: decay heat. Bottom: difference.

4. METHOD EXTENSION TO LONG TRANSIENTS

4.1. Accumulation Curve

Short-lived precursors define the short-term ($t < 10^4$ s) dynamics and set the short-term equilibrium of decay heat at constant fission rate. This equilibrium is reached exponentially and appears steady for several thousand seconds (see Figure 2, *left*). In contrast, long-lived precursors continue to accumulate, causing the decay heat to increase gradually with time, as shown in Figure 2, *right*. This decay heat curve obtained under constant fission power, i.e. $P^{\text{fiss}}(t) = \text{const}$, is referred to as the *accumulation curve* $c(t)$.

The difference observed between the inverted growth curve and the decay curve in Figure 2 corresponds to the increase of the accumulation curve $c(t) - c(0)$. The function $c(t)$ can therefore be incorporated into the adaptive method to *correct* precursor group contributions during long on-power transients. To this end, the conditional form $c_i(t)$, together with the complement heat concept, will be applied to each group in analogy with Equations (3) to (5):

$$C_i^C(t) = -\Delta P_i^{\text{fiss}} \cdot [c_i(0) - c_i(t)]. \quad (15)$$

4.2. Adaptive Algorithm Extension to Long Transients

1. At the start of the simulation, initialize the decay heat table with correction for long transients:

$$H(t) := c(t) \cdot P(0). \quad (16)$$

2. At each calculation step j , check the change in fission power:
 - (a) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} \neq 0$, update the decay heat table: $H(t) := H(t) - H_j^C(t) - C_j^C(t)$.
 - (b) If $\Delta P_j^{\text{fiss}} = 0$, leave the decay heat table unchanged.
3. Extract the instantaneous decay heat from the updated table and repeat step 2.

4.3. Verification Results for Long Transients

Figure 4. Decay heat in power step-up scenario. Top: fission power. Middle: decay heat. Bottom: difference.

For verification, a power “step-up” scenario was analyzed in which the power was increased to 120%, then returned to 100% after 100 s (see Figure 4). The adaptive method reproduced the Serpent reference solution with high accuracy. Beyond $\sim 10^4$ s, this agreement was preserved only by applying the correction for long on-power transients introduced in this section. The difference, primarily attributed to the exponential fits used to represent the $h(t)$ and $c(t)$ curves, did not exceed 0.06%.

5. LOAD-FOLLOWING DEMONSTRATION

To demonstrate the feasibility of the adaptive method for reactor applications, the decay heat evolution over one week of load-following was analyzed. The relative power history was taken from the French nuclear fleet in week 18 of 2025, provided by ENTSO-E in 15 min intervals (see Figure 5).

The adaptive method reproduced the Serpent reference solution with high accuracy, as the deviation from the reference did not exceed 0.15%. While both solutions were in close agreement, the computational costs differed by orders of magnitude. The Serpent calculation of this 671-step problem required on the order of *days* (e.g., about 45 h on an AMD 64-core EPYC 7713 at 2.0 GHz), whereas the adaptive algorithm executed the same problem within *fractions of a second* on a standard PC.

6. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This study presented an *adaptive method* for real-time decay heat estimation in arbitrary reactor transients without reliance on decay heat standards or real-time nuclide tracking. Building on the original formulation for non-SCRAM shutdowns, the method was extended in two key directions:

Figure 5. Decay heat in load-following scenario. Top: fission power based on French nuclear power generation in week 18 of 2025 (source: ENTSO-E). Middle: decay heat. Bottom: difference.

1. transients with both decreasing and increasing power (e.g., load-following regimes), and
2. long-duration transients by accounting for the accumulation of long-lived precursors.

Verification against Serpent Monte Carlo depletion calculations demonstrated that the method:

- has high accuracy without requiring real-time nuclide tracking or a standards;
- is orders of magnitude faster than Monte Carlo depletion, enabling real-time simulations;
- requires only a precomputed SCRAM curve for short transients ($t < 10^4$ s);
- allows simulation of arbitrary scenarios without prior knowledge of the transient power;
- requires only one additional accumulation curve to preserve accuracy in long on-power transients; and
- is design-independent and well suited for advanced reactor applications.

Future work will focus on benchmarking this method against traditional decay heat estimation approaches.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Nikitin, E. Fridman, and A. Ponomarev. "An Adaptive Model for Decay Heat Estimation Using Scram Curves." In *PHYSOR 2024*, pp. 1838–1844. San Francisco, CA (2024).
- [2] J. Leppänen, M. Pusa, T. Viitanen, V. Valtavirta, and T. Kaltiaisenaho. "The Serpent Monte Carlo Code: Status, Development and Applications in 2013." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 82, pp. 142–150 (2015).
- [3] E. Nikitin. "Adaptive Decay Heat Estimation for Non-SCRAM Shutdowns: Verification and Application." In *Innovation in Thermal Hydraulics for Nuclear Future NURETH-21*. Busan, Republic of Korea (2025).
- [4] J. D. Bess. "Evaluation of the Initial Isothermal Physics Measurements at the Fast Flux Test Facility, a Prototypic Liquid Metal Fast Breeder Reactor." In *International Handbook of Evaluated Reactor Physics Benchmark Experiments*. NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1, FFTF-LMFR-RESR-001, revision 2, OECD Nuclear Energy Agency (2019).